

SCIENCE FUNDERS: COMMITMENTS TOWARDS OPEN INFRASTRUCTURE

This document has been produced by the members of the “Infrastructure for Open Scholarship” Working Group emerging from the CERN-NASA Summit in July 2023.

After the 2023 CERN-NASA Summit “Accelerating the Adoption of Open Science”, a group of participants highlighted the need for science funders to consider **infrastructure as a key prerequisite of open science policies**. The experts understand that current lack of support for the mechanisms for sharing data, articles, code, and designs is undermining effective adoption of open science.

The goal of these principles is to provide high-level orientation to science funders, including national councils, universities, and research institutes, so open infrastructure has the support it needs for sustainable open science strategies. It consists of a core set of principles plus a desirable list of recommendations for those already addressing infrastructure in open science.

By infrastructure, we mean:

The sets of services, protocols, standards, and software that the academic ecosystem needs to perform its functions throughout the research lifecycle — from the earliest phases of research, collaboration, and experimentation through data collection and storage, data organization, data analysis and computation, authorship, submission, review and annotation, copyediting, publishing, archiving, citation, discovery, and more. Human labor involved in the development and maintenance of the infrastructure is a critical part of what we consider infrastructure.

Definition from [Invest in Open Infrastructure](#)

These recommendations for funders are accompanied by a set of principles for open infrastructure projects that complements the first set and aims to increase the quality of service provided to researchers and institutions. The group aims to emphasize that the principles for infrastructure initiatives do not have a prescriptive approach; instead the goal should be to foster good practices in the field.

This work intends to add and build on the corpus of work that has been undertaken globally in this area, some of which is referenced at the end of this document. As any global framework, it will need to be regionally situated to ensure feasibility, efficacy and sustainability in a diversity of contexts.

By open infrastructure, we refer to:

The narrower sets of services, protocols, standards and software that can empower communities to collectively build the systems and infrastructures that deliver new improved collective benefits without restrictions, and for a healthy global interrelated infrastructure system. Open infrastructure should be situated, as open as possible but as closed as necessary considering privacy and security requirements.

Core principles for science funders

Infrastructure in open scholarship policies	Funders must ensure open infrastructure considerations are part of open scholarship policies, and shared externally as good practice.
Recognizing work	Funders must ensure work on open infrastructures is properly recognized and sustained, including appropriately resourcing for set up, maintenance, and community governance and management roles.
Fund and support	Funders should support infrastructure work associated with compliance with their open scholarship policies, including but not limited to discoverability, access and quality review of scholarly outputs, maintenance and updates of infrastructure, and provision of user support.
Capabilities	Funders should promote institutions in building competencies to develop, maintain, and contribute to open infrastructure for relevant researchers and professional support staff that are defined in standard role descriptions.
Transparency	Funders should promote open infrastructures which are transparent about their governance, resources (both human and technical), funding source, and what is the value of the infrastructure.

Further recommendations for science funders

Open source	Funders should promote open infrastructures to be open source – all software and assets required to run the infrastructure should be available under an open-source license. This does not include other software that may be involved with running the organization.
Harmonizing compliance	Funders should promote and support infrastructures that allow ease of compliance with public access and open science policies, by enabling an environment of community standards monitored and evaluated under public oversight.
Scalability and collaboration	Funders should promote interoperability and portability to enhance and reuse open infrastructures, promoting collaborations rather than risking unnecessary system-level duplication.
Governance	Funders should promote mission-driven, cooperatively-created, and stakeholder-governed infrastructures.
Open data	Funders should mandate open infrastructures to make data as open and available as possible, as closed as necessary (within constraints of privacy laws and international security law). The CCO waiver is the best practice in making data openly and legally available. Privacy and data protection laws as well as export control legislation will limit the extent to which this is possible.

Core principles for infrastructure initiatives

Free and Easy Access	The infrastructure provides broad, equitable, and maximally open access to research outputs and their metadata free of charge in a timely manner after submission, consistent with legal and policy requirements.
Unique Persistent Identifiers	The infrastructure assigns citable, unique persistent identifiers (PID or DPI, OrcID), such as a digital object identifier (ARKs, handles, DOIs, or other systems), to support discovery, reporting of research progress, research institutions (ROR), and research assessment. The unique PID points to a persistent location that remains accessible even if the dataset is de-accessioned or no longer available.
Long-term Technical Sustainability	The infrastructure has a plan for long-term management of research outputs, building on a stable technical infrastructure and funding plans; terms of use are clearly and publicly stated.
Curation and Quality Assurance	The infrastructure provides or facilitates expert curation and quality assurance to improve the accuracy and integrity of research outputs and metadata.
Provenance	The infrastructure has mechanisms in place to record the origin, chain of custody, version control, and any other modifications to submitted outputs and metadata. Archives adopt standard practices for data preservation.

Further recommendations for infrastructure initiatives

Risk Management	The infrastructure has documented capabilities for ensuring that administrative, technical, and physical safeguards are employed to comply with applicable confidentiality, risk management, and continuous monitoring requirements for sensitive data. A plan is in place for how content will be archived or migrated if the infrastructure ceases to exist.
Retention Policy	The infrastructure should be able to integrate institutional retention policies into their own data retention workflows.
Common Format	The infrastructure allows research outputs and metadata to be accessed, downloaded, or exported from the repository in widely used, preferably non-proprietary, formats consistent with standards used in the disciplines the repository serves.
Authentication	The infrastructure supports authentication of data submitters. The repository has technical capabilities that facilitate associating submitter PIDs with those assigned to their deposited digital objects.
Protocols	Communications and data exchange use open standards for data formats and protocols.

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How to cite this work

Science funders: commitments towards open infrastructure. CERN-NASA Working Group “Infrastructure for Open Scholarship”. May 2024. Available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11444361>

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Acknowledgements

We would like to thank members of the working group “Open Infrastructure” for their insights and productive discussions. Special thanks to the CERN Open Science team and the NASA TOPS initiative for their continuous support.

This work was funded by the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation.

